

Effect of Age and Drying Methods on Chemical Composition and Bacterial Load of Cattle Minced Meat

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Abstract

Meat preservation by drying has been practised for many thousands of years. Reducing the moisture content (dehydration) to prevent food spoilage is a well-known method in tropical areas. In this study, minced meat from three different age groups X (2-3), Y (3-4) and Z (4-5) years were dried using three different drying methods. The study was conducted to investigate the best methods of drying meat and to assess the chemical composition values and the amount of total bacterial account for minced dried meat. All the experimental data were statistically analysed using complete randomized design (CRD) in factorial arrangement (3X3X3) using SPSS, computer program package and Duncan multiple range tests used to detect differences between means. In terms of chemical composition, the results showed highly significant differences ($P < 0.01$) between treatments for crude protein, moisture content, fat content and ash. On the other hand, the study observed that there were highly significant differences ($P < 0.01$) among treatments for total bacterial count, *E. coli spp* cfu/g, *Staphylococci spp* cfu/g and *Salmonella spp* cfu/g. Generally, in this study, the sun drying minced meat (SDMM) and fan drying minced meat (FDMM) for both small age and medium age had the highest values and positive results on fat content, ash percentage clear lowest bacterial total account, *E. coli spp* cfu/g, *Staphylococci spp* cfu/g, and *Salmonella spp* cfu/g, while

room temperature dried minced meat for small and medium age recorded the highest values of crude protein. Sun drying of minced meat with different age of slaughtered animals score positive results on chemical composition bacterial total account, *E. coli spp* cfu/g, *Staphylococci spp* cfu/g and *Salmonella spp* cfu/g content so It is recommended to use sun drying as the best method for preservation drying meat.

Keywords: *minced meat, meat drying, Bacterial load, crude protein, moisture, fat and ash.*

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Introduction

Preservation of meat by the sun drying has been practiced for many thousands of years. Lowering the moisture content (dehydration) to prevent foods from spoilage is a well-known method in tropical areas. Such dried meat products are known as biltong in South Africa, charqui in South America, pemmican in North America, Tassajo in Uruguay, and dendeng in Indonesia (Lawrie, 1985). (Williams, 2002), reported that red meat contains high biological value protein and important micronutrients that are needed for good health throughout life. (Hassan *et al.*, 2024) reported that sex, age and species of animal effects on meat chemical composition. Sun drying is the most widely used method of food preservation in the world. It is a straightforward and affordable process. This method is popular, but it has a lot of disadvantages, such as weather dependence and contamination from insects, dust, dirt, and sand particles. Furthermore, it may take a while for everything to dry. (Elhesain *et al.*, 2023). Drying is one of the oldest methods of food preservation, but it's also a difficult food processing process because it makes the dried product's quality poor sometimes. To further improve food durability, drying is one of the most widely used methods. (Abdalla., *et al.*, 2023). Large amounts of meat are lost annually as a result of improper handling during storage and preservation. This is because meat has a high moisture content, which causes microorganisms like insects and mites to thrive and expand at a very quick rate. Fish is one of those foods that spoils quickly in terms of both quantity and quality. (HA, E. *et al.*, 2021). Drying is one of the standard methods to reduce water content in food. (Abdalla., *et al.*, 2023). The sun drying method can be done at the domestic or farm level for quick and uncomplicated preservation for example of surplus meat which cannot be consumed immediately or stored properly. Possible contamination can be limited at the small-scale level, as these operations are easy to manage and supervise. (FAO, 2007).

Empey and Scott, 1983 found that hides contained 3.3×10^6 organism/cm of hide surface, airborne contamination was found to be 1.6×10^6 organism/ml. They further reported that organisms derived from infected person or healthy carriers include *Salmonella spp*, *Shigella spp*, *E. coli*, *Staph albus* and *Staph aureus*. (Ajiboye *et al.*, 2011) reported that the dried meat samples were contaminated with microorganisms despite the dried and hard texture of the meat. Bacteria isolated from the dried meat were *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Micrococcus luteus*, *Neisseria sp* and *Acinetobacter sp*. Fungi isolated include *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Rhizopus sp* and *Penicillium sp*. Many authors interest study effects of many methods of preservation food (Babiker, *et al.* 2024), (Hassan *et al.*, 2024), (Elhesain, *et al.*, 2023), (HA, E. *et al.*, 2021).and Tiwari, (2002).

Objectives of the Study

General objective

The general objective of this study is to evaluate the effect of using different methods of drying on chemical composition and bacterial load of cattle grinded meat

Specific objectives

1. To assess the effect of using different methods of drying on nutritive value of meat.
2. To assess the amount of bacterial total count with using different methods of drying.

Material and Methods

Site of the Study

This study comprised three different methods of meat drying: sun dry, fan dry and room temperature dry. For both minced and slices meat (*Sharmoot*) which conducted at the Nutrition and Microbiology laboratory, Faculty of Animal Production –University of Khartoum, Sudan.

Experimental Units

Three samples of meat were selected from the male beef according to the age at the following:

X (2-3) years of age as small age group

Y (3-4) years of age as medium age group

Z (4-5) years of age as big age group

Samples Collection

Different sample of meat were collected according to the animal age (average age of each group), from the well-known butcher at Khartoum slaughter house after deboning, classification, minced and dried with different methods

Experimental Grouping

Three methods of meat drying used with three categories of minced meat as the following

Treatment A Sun-dried minced meat (SDMM)

Treatment B Fan dried minced meat (FDMM)

Treatment C Room temperature dried minced meat (RDMM)

Experimental Units' Preparation

Each sample of meat was carefully prepared according to the age (X, Y and Z) grinding, dried and backed in label bags waiting chemical and microbiological analysis.

Experimental Equipment

Knife with different size and functions

Silent cutter

Sensitive balance.

Electric grinder.

Electric mincing machine

Dishes with different size and function

Nylon bags.

Spoon.

Flat ion dishes

Flour fans.

Data Collection

Chemical analysis

Moisture content, crud protein fat content and ash content were determined according to methods of the Association of Official Analytical chemists (AOAC, 1997).

Microbial Parameters

Bacterial total count

One ml aliquots from suitable dilution were transferred aseptically into sterile Petri dishes. To each dilution, 10–15 mls of melted and cooled (42°C) plate count agar was added. Inoculums was mixed well with the medium and allowed to solidify. The plates were then incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. The total viable count was calculated by the standard formula:

$$\frac{S}{S+D} \cdot PC = TCFU \quad (1)$$

Salmonella *E. coli* and *Staphylococcus* detection

Ten grams of sample were weighed aseptically and mixed well with 100 mls sterile distilled water, and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. Then 10 ml were drawn aseptically and added to 100 ml selenite broth. The broth was incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. Then with a loop full streaking was done on Salmonella *E. coli* and *Staphylococcus* agar plates. plates were incubated at 37°C for 72 hours. Black metallic sheen discrete colonies indicated the presence of *salmonella spp E. coli* and *Staphylococcus spp*.

Statistical Analysis

The data of the experiments was statistically analyzed by using statistical package for Social Studies (SPSS version 23.0).3X3X3 A factorial Completely Randomized Design (CRD) (Steel and Torrie, 1980) arrangement will be used for means separation among treatment. One way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used for means separation between means and Duncan Multiple Range Tests (DMRT) was used to detect difference between means (Snedcor and Cochran, 1980).

Results

Table 1. Average Values (Means±SE) of Chemical Composition for Minced Dried Meat

Factor A (Age group/yrs)	Crud protein	Moisture	Fat	Ash
X (2-3) Small age	48.80 ^b	5.28 ^b	11.50 ^b	8.56 ^{ab}
Y (3-4) Medium age	51.10 ^a	5.33 ^b	21.70 ^a	6.60 ^c
Z (4-5) Big age	52.93 ^a	6.80 ^a	22.73 ^a	7.40 ^b
S. E	0.55	0.44	0.40	0.36
Sig	**	**	**	**
Factor B (Treatments group)				
A (Sun drying)	50.94 ^c	5.80 ^b	20.21 ^b	7.52 ^a
B (Fan drying)	53.13 ^b	6.15 ^a	19.10 ^b	6.05 ^b
C (Room temperature drying)	66.00 ^a	6.16 ^a	21.07 ^a	7.38 ^a
S. E	0.55	0.44	0.40	0.36
Sig	**	**	**	**

In this table and next tables: Sig = Level of significance, S.E = Standard error of the treatment means, N.S. = Not significantly different, * = Significant different at 0.05 and mean in columns followed by the same letter subscript are not significantly different (P>0.05).

Table 2. Effect of Interaction between Age Factor and Treatment Factor of Chemical Composition for Minced Dried Meat

Factor A * Factor B	Crud protein	Moisture	Fat	Ash
X (2-3) Small age				
Sun dry	49.80	5.29	11.30	8.54
Fan drying	51.40	5.35	19.70	6.61
Room temperature drying	52.53	6.90	17.93	7.43
S. E	0.55	0.44	0.40	0.36
Y (3-4) Medium age				
Sun dry	51.94	5.80	20.22	7.53
Fan drying	53.13	6.25	19.11	6.10
Room temperature drying	65.00	6.22	21.10	7.37
S. E	0.55	0.44	0.40	0.36
Z (4-5) Big age				
Sun dry	51.15	5.85	19.97	7.63
Fan drying	56.82	6.09	20.14	7.00
Room temperature drying	54.50	5.97	21.06	7.23
S. E	0.55	0.44	0.40	0.36
Sig	*	*	*	*

Table 3. Average Values (Means±SE) of Bacterial Total Account cfu/g for Minced Dried Meat

Factor A (Age group/yrs)	Bacterial total account cfu/g	E. coli spp cfu/g	Staphylococci spp cfu/g	Salmonella spp cfu/g
X (2-3) Small age	7.5x10 ^{2c}	7.00 ^b	0.70x10 ^{2c}	-
Y (3-4) Medium age	6.3x10 ^{3b}	12.00 ^a	1.20x10 ^{2b}	-
Z (4-5) Big age	6.9x10 ^{3a}	9.00 ^b	1.70x10 ^{2a}	-
S. E	7.60	0.42	0.32	0.00
Sig	**	**	**	NO
Factor B (Treatments group)				
A (Sun drying)	6.1x10 ^{3b}	8.33 ^c	2.1x10 ^{2c}	+
B (Fan drying)	6.43x10 ^{3b}	14.33 ^a	3.6x10 ^{2b}	+
C (Room temperature drying)	7.13x10 ^{3a}	10.67 ^b	5.0x10 ^{2a}	++
S. E	7.60	0.42	0.32	00
Sig	**	**	**	**

Note: In this table and next tables: Sig = Level of significance, S.E = Standard error of the treatment means, N.S. = Not significantly different, * = Significant different at 0.05 and mean in columns followed by the same letter subscript are not significantly different (P>0.05).

Table 4. Average Values (Means±SE) of Isolated Bacterial Total Account cfu/g for Minced Dried Meat

Factor A * Factor B	Bacterial total account cfu/g	E. coli spp cfu/g	Staphylococci spp cfu/g
X (2-3) Small age			
Sun dry	7.5x10 ²	7.00	00.00

Fan drying	7.1x10 ³	8.00	00.00
Room temperature drying	5.1x10 ³	10.0	5.0x10 ²
S. E	7.60	0.42	0.32
Y (3-4) Medium age			
Sun dry	6.3x10 ³	12.00	00.00
Fan drying	8.0x10 ³	14.00	00.00
Room temperature drying	6.2x10 ³	17.30	3.6x10 ²
S. E	7.60	0.42	0.32
Z (4-5) Big age			
Sun dry	6.9x10 ³	9.00	00.00
Fan drying	4.2x10 ³	10.00	00.00
Room temperature drying	7.1x10 ³	13.00	2.1x10 ²
S. E	7.60	0.42	0.32
Sig	*	*	*

Discussion

Crud Protein Content

Average value of crude protein percentages for different minced meat in Table (1). The study showed highly significant differences ($P < 0.01$) among the treatments for protein content. According to the age group Z and group Y had scored the highest values of crude protein while group X tended to reported the less values of protein content. Due to treatment factor treatment C (room temperature drying) reported the highest values of crud protein followed by treatment B (fan drying) while treatment A (sun drying) reported the less values. Concerning to interaction between age group factor and treatment group factor of crud protein for minced dried meat table (2) group Y (medium age) with treatment C (room temperature drying) reported the highest values of crud protein followed by Z Group with treatment B (fan drying) while X group with treatment A (sun drying) recorded the less values of crud protein. that is referred to effect of age and type of meat processed (FAO, 2007). reported that processing of meat provides high nutritional value product, rich in protein and fat. Treatment C (room temperature drying) with Y age group tended to reported the highest values of crude protein.

Moisture Content

Table (1) showed the values of moisture content. The study showed highly significant differences ($P < 0.01$) among the treatments for moisture content. concerning to the age group Z group reported the highest values of moisture while group X and group Y reported the less values. According to treatment group treatment B (fan drying) and treatment C (room temperature) recorded the highest values of moisture content while treatment A (sun drying) reported the less values of moisture content. table (2) showed interaction between age group factor and treatment group factor of moisture for minced dried meat, X group with room temperature drying reported the highest values of moisture content followed by Z group with fan drying while X group with fan drying tended to have the less values of moisture.

Fat Content

Average values of fat content for different minced meat shown in Table (1). The study showed highly significant differences ($P < 0.01$) among the treatments for fat content. According to the age group Z and Y group had reported the highest values of fat percentage while group X reported le less values. Due to treatment group factor, group C reported the highest values of fat content while treatment A and treatment B reported the less values. Concerning to interaction effect between age group factor and treatment group factor of fat content for minced dried meat table (2), Y group with room temperature drying and Z group with room temperature drying reported the highest values of moisture content and X group with sun drying reported the less value.

Ash Content

Average values of ash content for different minced meat shown in Table (1). The study showed highly significant differences ($P < 0.01$) among the treatments for ash content. According to the age group X group had reported the highest values of ash percentage followed by group Z while group Y reported less values. According to treatment group factor, group C reported the highest values of fat content while treatment A and treatment B reported the less values. Concerning to interaction effect between age group factor and treatment group factor of ash content for minced dried meat table (2), X group with sun drying reported the highest value followed by Z group with sun drying while Y group with fan drying reported the less value.

Bacterial Total Account cfu/g for Minced Dried Meat

Average values of bacterial total account for different minced meat shown in Table (3). The study showed highly significant differences ($P < 0.01$) among age group and treatments group. According to the age group Z group reported the highest value of bacterial load followed by Y group while X group reported the values. Due to treatment factor treatment C reported the highest values of bacterial load while treatment B and treatment A reported the less values. Concerning to interaction between age group factor and treatment group factor of bacterial load for minced dried meat table (4) group Y with treatment B reported the highest values of bacterial load followed by group X with treatment A and group Z with treatment C while group X with treatment A recorded the less values.

E. coli spp cfu/g

Average values of *E. coli spp* for different minced meat shown in Table (3.) The study showed highly significant differences ($P < 0.01$) among age group and treatments group. Concerning to the age group Y group reported the highest value of *E. coli spp* followed by group Z while group X reported the less values. According to treatment factor treatment B reported the highest values of *E. coli spp* followed by treatment C while treatment A reported the less values. Concerning to interaction between age group factor and treatment group factor of *E. coli spp* for minced dried meat table (4) group Y with treatment C reported the highest values of *E. coli spp* followed by Y Group with treatment B while group X with treatment A recorded the less values.

Staphylococci spp cfu/g

Average values of *Staphylococci spp* for different minced meat shown in Table (3.) The study showed highly significant differences ($P < 0.01$) among age group and treatments group. Due to the age group Z group reported the highest value of *Staphylococci spp* followed by group Y while group X reported the less values. According to treatment factor treatment C reported the highest values of *Staphylococci spp* followed by treatment B while treatment A reported the less values. Concerning to interaction between age group factor and treatment group factor of *Staphylococci spp* table (4) group X with treatment C reported the highest values *Staphylococci spp* followed by Y Group with treatment C while group Z with treatment C recorded the less values.

Salmonella spp cfu/g

Average values of *Salmonella spp* for different minced meat shown in Table (3.) The study observed no significantly ($P \geq 0.05$) differences between age factor. On the other hand, the study showed highly significant differences ($P < 0.01$) among treatments group factor. Treatment C reported the highest values of *Salmonella spp* while treatment A and B reported the less values.

Conclusion

The age of animal (Cow) where is small, medium or big and the drying method were affected the chemical composition and bacterial total count of the Cattle Minced Meat (*cfu/g*) highly significant.

References

- Abdalla, M., Babiker, A. M. O. A., Khair, U. E. H. M., Elhesain, M. H. A., Idriss, S. H. E., Sulieman, O., & Figeada, A. (2023). Comparative study between open-direct sun and solar drying of onion slices (*Allium cepa* L.). *OPSearch: American Journal of Open Research*, 2(6), 226–234. <https://doi.org/10.58811/opsearch.v2i6.16>
- Ajiboye, E. A., Sani, A., Adedayo, R. M., Kolawole, M. O., & Oladosu, O. T. (2011). Physicochemical properties and microorganisms isolated from dried meat obtained in Oja-Oba market in Ilorin, Nigeria. *Advances in Applied Research*, 2(4), 391–400.
- Association of Official Analytical Chemists. (1997). *Official methods of analysis* (14th ed.).
- Babiker, A. M. O. A., Elhesain, M. H. A., Widatalla, M. M., Idriss, S. H. E., Hassan, H. E., & Sahal, K. E. (2024). Effect of solar dryer and direct open sun drying methods on drying air temperatures and moisture content of fish Bayad (*Bagrus bayad*). *European Journal of Ecology, Biology and Agriculture*, 1(2), 1–5. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejeba.2024.1\(2\).01](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejeba.2024.1(2).01)
- Elhesain, M., Mustafa, W., Abdalla, M., & Bukhari, M. (2023). Comparative study between different drying methods using thin-layers of mango slices (*Mangifera indica* L.). *Food Technology Research Journal*, 2(3), 101–110. <http://dx.doi.org/10.21608/ftj.2023.334165>
- Empey, W. A., & Scott, W. J. (1983). Investigation on chilled beef: I. Microbial contamination acquired in the meat works. *Bulletin of the Council for Scientific and Industrial Research*, (126).
- Food and Agriculture Organization. (2007). *Meat processing technology for small- to medium-scale producers*. RAP Publication, Bangkok, Thailand.
- Ha, E. M., Em, O. O., & Ne, S. W. (2021). Fish drying using different drying methods at different temperatures for fish *Tilapia nilotica* (*Oreochromis niloticus*). *Bulletin of Voronezh State University of Engineering Technologies*, 83(3), 115–120.
- Hassan, H. E., Sahal, K. E., Elhashmi, Y. H., Mousa, A. M., Abdelmageed, M. E. I., Tameem Eldar, A. A., Mortada, H. A. E., & Babiker, A. M. O. A. (2024). Effect of sex and age on chemical composition of sheep, cattle, and camel meat. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Growth Evaluation*, 5(2), 92–98.
- Lawrie, R. A. (1985). *Meat science* (4th ed.). Pergamon Press.
- Snedecor, G. W., & Cochran, W. G. (1980). *Statistical methods* (7th ed.). Iowa State University Press.
- Steel, R. G., & Torrie, J. H. (1980). *Principles and procedures of statistics* (2nd ed.). McGraw-Hill.
- Tiwari, G. N. (2002). *Solar energy: Fundamentals, design, modeling, and applications*. Narosa Publishing House.
- Williams, O. J. (2002). Capture and handling of camels destined for the abattoir. Central Australian Camel Industry Association and Rural Industry Research and Development Corporation.

